

SOME REMARKS ON THE MOON'S DIAMETER AND THE ECLIPSE TABLES IN BABYLONIAN ASTRONOMY

By Dr. A. Pannekoek, Amsterdam.

1. After the first pioneer work of J. Epping it was F. X. Kugler who, by his studies of cuneigraph tablets copied by Strassmaier, was able to show the high development and the special character of Chaldaean astronomy in the last centuries B. C. Fragments of a number of tablets were found and deciphered, containing ephemeris of the moon and the planets. In these ephemeris the periodic inequalities in the motion of the heavenly bodies are taken into account. Not by means of sinus functions, as in Greek astronomy, that was based on the geometrical model of circular orbits and epicycles. But by means of purely arithmetical or algebraic operations. Among the tables containing the consecutive full moons or the consecutive new moons Kugler¹⁾ found two different systems of calculation. In the so-called 2nd system two different values for the velocity of the sun were adopted for the two opposite parts of the ecliptic. In the 1st system this velocity—in the form of the arc of the ecliptic between the consecutive full moons—varied regularly between two fixed limits, always with exactly the same difference increasing or decreasing, the upward course being reflected and turning downward at the upper limit, the downward course turning upward where it reaches the lower limit. So the values can be represented by equidistant points situated on straight lines running zig-zag between two limits. This method of representation and computation is used also in the planetary tables.

In the lunar tables of the 2nd system it was especially the column of values, designated E by Kugler, that offered great difficulties. Kugler found that they fluctuate between the limits $\pm 7,12,0$ (All values are given in sexagesimal fractions, the consecutive sexagesimals are here separated by comma's, following Neugebauer) and designate in some way the moon's latitude or a function of it. They are situated on a zig-zag line which in its middle part, between $\pm 2,24,0$ has twice the inclination of its outer parts. Their constant differences (on the outer parts) are $2,6,15,42$ over 194° of the ecliptic, $1,58,45,42$ over the remaining 166° of the ecliptic. Neugebauer, who gave an exact mathematical theory for the structure of these Chaldaean tables and so was able to connect all the different fragments and to determine their date, gives the following simple representation of the latitude values. First a regular zig-zag line between $\pm 6,0,0$ (called "centre function" by Neugebauer, and designated E') is constructed with the same

¹⁾ F. X. Kugler S. J. Die Babylonische Mondrechnung. 1900. (quoted here as BMR).

turning points. Then to find the function E (called E'' by Neugebauer) all values E' beyond 1,12,0 are increased by the amount of 1,12,0 and all lower values are doubled. The numerical values are followed each by two signs, read U and LAL, in different arrangement, the one standing first evidently indicating northern or southern latitude, the other the upward or downward direction of the moon's motion.

The centre function forms an easy contrivance to deduce the period relations. After having proceeded $4 \times 6,0,0$ it returns to the same maximum or minimum. The mean increase per synodic month is somewhat complicated to derive, since for one part (166°) of the ecliptic, during $5\frac{2}{3}\frac{0}{3}\frac{3}{3}$ months it increases 1,58,45,42 per month, for the other part (194°), during $6\frac{7}{15}$ months it increases 2,6,15,42 per month. The mean increase is 2,2,40,58¹). Hence the ratio of the draconitic and the synodic month is 26,2,40,58 to 24. Neugebauer, by somewhat simplifying this relation finds 242 : 223 for it, which means that the well known saros period 223 synodic months = 242 draconitic months should hold good here. If this should hold good exactly, the mean increase of the centre function per month would have been 2,2,41,26; we do not see any reason why values smaller by 0,0,0,28 should have been adopted in the construction of the tables. With the values adopted the increase of the centre function in 223 synodic months is $223 \times 24 + 455, 58, 15, 34$, hence 0,1,44,26 smaller than the increase 242×24 in 242 draconitic months. Now 223 synodic months are indeed 0.0357 days shorter than 242 draconitic months; this difference corresponds to a difference of 0,1,53 in the "centre function", only a little more than the Chaldaean difference. It seems probable, therefore, that in system II a more accurate ratio of the two periods has been used than the simple ratio of the saros relation; though not so accurate as the ratio 5458 : 5923 used in system I and by Hipparchus.

To the moon tables of the 2nd system belongs also an eclipse table, designated 81—7—6 No. 93 in Kugler's work, No. 107 by Neugebauer. It gives the same columns up to E as the full moon tables, but only for the full moons at which an eclipse may be possible. In the Babylonian chronology, which reckons with true lunar months, beginning each month with the appearance of the evening sickle, and intercalating repeatedly a 13th month, these eclipse moons follow one another, as a rule, with intervals of 6 months. After six lunar months the longitude of the sun and the full moon have increased on the average by $174^\circ \cdot 65$, the nodes have receded $9^\circ \cdot 38$, so that the full moon relative to the node has advanced $4^\circ \cdot 03$. Since for a total eclipse the distance of the full moon to the node must not exceed 5° or 6° , for a partial eclipse not 10° or 12° , we will have a consecutive series of 5 or 6 eclipses, beginning with partial eclipses when that distance from -12° increases to -6° , then 2 or 3 total eclipses when it increases from -6 to $+6$, and ending with partial eclipses, till this distance surpasses $+12$. Then the series ceases; but soon the preceding full moons, for which that distance is $30^\circ \cdot 7$ smaller, approach the nodes and a new series begins. Hence at the

¹) cf. O. Neugebauer, *Untersuchungen zur antiken Astronomie*, III, p. 238 (Quellen und Studien, Bd. 4).

6,0,0; if we identify it with our inclination of the moon's orbit 5° the unit used appears to be $\frac{1}{3} \times 2^\circ \cdot 5 = \frac{1}{3}$ ammat. Then the diameter of the moon $2 \times 1,12,0$ in the same unit corresponds to 2° : "that the system II adopts a lunar diameter of 2° , exactly the same value that Aristarch of Samos assumed in his work on the size and distances of sun and moon. So the most discussed problem of the origin of this much too large value is solved in a simple way"¹⁾. The constant value 17,24 occurring in the ψ values clearly indicates the radius of the earth's shadow: " ψ gives the distance of a point with latitude E'' of the moon from the border line of a zone $2c$ wide with the ecliptic as its line of symmetry, measured from the ingressborder in the direction of the passage through the node. c denotes the apparent radius of the earth's shadow at the moon's distance, hence ψ is the depth the point E'' immersed into the shadow, measured in digits"²⁾.

If we write it $10 \times 1,44,24$ it appears to be expressed in a unit 10 times smaller than the unit of E'' , viz. $\frac{1}{30}$ ammat, which also is found in other texts and is usually translated as "digit". Then the radius of the shadow, in our units, is $1^\circ 27'$. This value also is much too large. In the maximum duration of a total eclipse, however, the errors are compensated because it depends on the difference of the diameters. Neugebauer assumes that by means of this duration the shadow's diameter has been deduced from the moon's diameter. "From a false measurement of the size of the moon's disc and the rightly observed maximum duration of circa 2 hours of the totality of a lunar eclipse the value of circa 3° for the size of the earth's shadow has been calculated"³⁾.

We must express some doubts as to the validity of these conclusions. They are founded entirely on the supposition, that the increase by 1,12,0 represents the transition from centre to border of the moon, which is only an assumption. Why should we go from the centre to this border? The visibility of an eclipse, it is true, directly depends not on the centre but on the border; but it is not the outer border with latitude E'' but the inner border that by its immersion depth into the earth's shadow determines the darkened part in the partial eclipses. It is well known what an important role in the divination was played by the situation of the darkened parts in the partial eclipses as well as in the partial phases of the total eclipses. It is true that the position of the outer border to the shadow determines whether an eclipse would be total. But total eclipses take place for much smaller latitudes only, when E'' did not exceed a value of nearly 0,52. In this extreme case this value is got by doubling the latitude of the centre, hence increasing not by 1,12,0 but only by 0,26 or less. In these cases then, where the outer border could play a role in the eclipse phenomena, the "border function" has nothing to do with the moon's border. Hence it must be considered doubtful whether the increase of 1,12,0 has any connection with the moon's diameter.

Neither is it probable that the Chaldaean astronomers have really assumed

¹⁾ Neugebauer, U. A. A. III, p. 269.

²⁾ l. c. p. 288.

³⁾ l. c. p. 289.

the moon's diameter to be 2° and that of the earth's shadow to be 3° . Certainly their instruments or contrivances for angular measurements, if they had any, were imperfect; but it is hardly credible that by means of them they should have found the moon's size four times too large. Moreover, there are phenomena where the difficultly measurable quantitative values appear in large, easily observable differences of a qualitative character. The maximum duration of a total eclipse (nearly 2 hours) is determined by the difference of the two diameters; so, as we have said, this difference of 1° was right. But their sum total in the same way determines the maximum duration of the partial phase. In the case of diameters 2° and 3° this duration should have been 10 hours; in reality it is only 4 hours. This difference, as well as its consequences, must have been discernible to Chaldaean astronomers, and it rules out the possibility of their really having assumed those large values.

The eclipse table itself, by its structure excludes these values. If they were right, partial eclipses would be possible with a moon's latitude of $2\frac{1}{2}^\circ$, at a distance of 30° from the node. The eclipse table, however, contains only full moons up to a distance of 15° or 16° from the node, with a value of E' , the "centre function" smaller than 1,0.

If the interpretation of the E'' column as latitudes of the moon's border is not right, we have to look for another. The representation of a sinusoidal function by a zig-zag line between the same extremes produces the largest errors in the vicinity of the zero line, the nodes. Here the slope is $\frac{1}{2}\pi = 1.57$ times too small. This may create difficulties when it is just these small values in the vicinity of zero that matter, that can be best observed, and that determine the phenomena. We could avoid these difficulties by increasing all values 1.57 times. In the case of the moon's motion in latitude, where the small latitudes then correctly determine the eclipse phenomena, this would mean that the maximum latitudes should be taken 8° instead of 5° . Since such a large value may be in contradiction even to rough measures or estimates of angular distance, there remains as an appropriate contrivance the use of a more complicated zig-zag line. It seems probable that the function E'' with its larger slope where it crosses the zero line, must be considered as a means of better adapting the latitude values to reality¹⁾.

The maximum 7,12,0 then corresponds to the real maximum latitude of the moon's centre. A comparison of the E'' values with the true sinus values for the "argument of latitude" $6^\circ, 12^\circ, 18^\circ, 24^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$ gives:

zig-zag line...	0,48,0	1,36,0	2,24,0	2,48,0	3,12,0	5,12,0	7,12,0
sinus line	0,45,8	1,29,49	2,13,29	2,55,41	3,36,0	6,11,31	7,12,0

The differences are small. The lower latitudes are somewhat too large, at most $\frac{1}{2}$ of their amount; far from the nodes the differences of course are larger. So this representation may be considered as entirely satisfactory for its purpose.

It depends on the value of the unit used in these numbers, what values of the diameters lie at the basis of these tables. If we assume, with Kugler and Neu-

¹⁾ This explanation has been suggested already by Kugler BMR p. 132.

gebauer, that the unit is $\frac{1}{3}$ of an ammat of $2^\circ \cdot 5$, then the maximum latitude corresponds to 6° and the limit for the occurrence of eclipses, 1,44,24 which now represents the limiting latitude of the moon's centre, hence the sum total of the radius of the moon and the shadow, is equal to $1^\circ 27'$. This is still too large; the real mean values are $15' 35''$ for the moon, $42' 8''$ for the earth's shadow, hence their sum total $57' 43''$, and their difference $26' 33''$. If we assume that the maximum latitude $7,12,0$ corresponds to the inclination 5° , then the sum total of the two radii is $1^\circ 12' \cdot 5$, already nearer to the truth. In this case three times the unit used would be $27\frac{1}{2}^\circ$. It must be remarked in this connection that Kugler, in determining the value of an ammat from the distances of planets to stars found, besides results about $2^\circ \cdot 5$, a number of values somewhat above and below $2^\circ 1'$.

3. It is to be doubted, however, whether the problem may be put in this form: what values for the diameter of the moon and the earth's shadow did the Chaldaean astronomers assume in their eclipse tables? They have not proceeded from measured diameters to compute their tables of the moon and the eclipses. Neither did they, probably, proceed in this way that from the eclipse phenomena they first derived the diameters to use them as the numerical basis for their tables. In a study of Chaldaean astronomy we must leave out entirely the basic elements of our astronomy and our modes of treatment. In our modern theory of the eclipses we proceed from the diameters and the conditions of tangency of the circles. The Babylonians, who had no predecessors in this realm, had to build up everything from its first beginnings; from their observations pursued during many centuries they found regularities and periods, which were used afterwards to construct tables for the future phenomena by means of purely numerical methods, without needing such notions as diameters of the heavenly bodies.

An illustration of this development is offered by comparison of this eclipse table Neug. 107 with an older table, the so-called Strassmaier "Saros-Canon"²⁾, formerly designated by Sp. II 71, now Neugebauer 200, which I have dealt with in a former publication³⁾. It gives a list of all consecutive eclipse full moons between 373 B. C. and 276 B. C., indicated solely by the year and the name of the month. Each column is divided by horizontal lines and the indication "5 months" into groups of 8 or 7. Each column consists of 5 such groups, 3 of 8 and 2 of 7 names, together 38 full moons, and then the series is continued in the next column. Hence such a column contains $(3 \times 7 + 2 \times 6) \times 6 + 5 \times 5 = 223$ months, the eclipse period, which in later times has been known as Saros. To show the basis of this arrangement, in the paper quoted, out of the known elements of the lunar motion, I constructed an analogous series of groups of eclipse moons⁴⁾. Added to each eclipse moon was a number m , giving in "digits" (twelfths

¹⁾ Kugler, Sternkunde und Sterndienst in Babel. (SSB) II, p. 549.

²⁾ Epping und Strassmaier, Ein babylonischer Saros-Canon. Zs. f. Assyriologie VIII, p. 176.

³⁾ The Origin of the Saros, Proc. Amsterdam Acad. Vol. XX, p. 943 (1917).

⁴⁾ l. c. p. 952.

of the moon's diameter) the distance of the inner border of the moon to the next border of the shadow; if $m < 0$ no eclipse takes place, if $m > 12$ the eclipse is total. A part of this table is reproduced in the present paper, with the difference that in the second half of each group, where m decreases after the node has been passed $44.5 - m = m'$ is put in its place. Now in each group m' begins with a small negative value, and increases regularly up to the end of the group; for m' between, say 12 and 32 the eclipse is total.

This table may be considered as an artificial model for the structure of the real eclipse tables, for **107** as well as for **200** for which it has been used in our former paper. In the next "Comparison of eclipse tables", we put beside the computed data of the model and those of the upper part of one column of **200** the corresponding data of the first part of **107**, viz. year and month, and the values

COMPARISON OF ECLIPSE TABLES

Computed model of an eclipse table		Text N ^o 200 5 th column		Text N ^o 107		
P	m'	Year S.E.	Month	Year S.E.	Month	ψ
+ 4.24	+31.8	Si 10	XI	137	II	17 27 50
+ 8.26	38.8	11	V	*	VIII	19 57 54
+ 12.29	47.9		XI	138	I	28 40 38
- 14.35	-13.3	12	IV 5m		VII	30 15 22
- 10.32	+ 1.6	*	X		XII 5m	0 18 12
- 6.29	8.2	13	III	139	VI	-1 32 24
- 2.27	18.3		IX		XII	10 59 0
+ 1.76	25.9	14	III	140	VI	9 2 24
+ 5.79	34.5		IX	*	XII	21 16 28
+ 9.81	42.0	15	III	141	V	20 15 12
+ 13.84	52.4	*	IX		XI	31 33 56
- 12.80	- 2.6	16	I 5m	142	V	31 28 0
- 8.77	+ 2.3		VII		X 5m	-0 13 50
- 4.75	13.6	17	I	143	III	3 5 34
- 0.72	19.7		VII		IX	10 3 38
+ 3.31	29.9	18	I	144	III	14 18 22
+ 7.33	36.3		VIa		IX	20 21 6
+ 11.36	47.8		XII	145	III	25 31 10
- 15.28	- 6.9	19	V 5m	*	IX	30 38 34
- 11.25	- 3.2		XI	146	II	36 43 58
- 7.22	+ 8.7	20	V		VII 5m	-1 8 2
- 3.20	14.5	*	XI	147	I	8 21 32
+ 0.83	24.9	21	IV		VII	9 8 16
+ 4.86	31.0		X	148	I	19 34 20
+ 8.89	42.6	22	IV	*	VII	19 25 44
+ 12.92	46.9		X		XIIa	30 47 8
- 13.72	- 7.2	23	III 5m	149	VI	29 43 12
etc.		etc.		etc.		etc.

* indicates that the year has a second 12th month Adaru.

of ψ . (All the other columns of this text, part of which have not yet been discussed, are omitted). Then we see that these ψ bear the same character as the m' , increasing in each of the groups, which are separated by the indication "5 months". This shows the meaning and the fundamental exactness of Neugebauer's explanation of the formation of the ψ columns. That the ψ , instead of the regular increase of the m' , show large irregularities in their increase, is due to the different solar velocity adopted for the two halves of the ecliptic and the alternating of the two opposite nodes in the series of eclipses. They are expressed in a larger unit than the m' , apparently about $\frac{1}{2}$ instead of $\frac{1}{2}$ of the moon's diameter. In **200** the groups had to be indicated by division lines, and the arrangement in columns by saros periods was necessary to indicate the return of the same consecutive series of aspects. In **107** this is not necessary, because it has been excerpted from a numerically computed moon table and because the values ψ are sufficient to indicate the different aspect of each eclipse.

There is still a difference between **107** and the computed table. The values of m' or ψ , for which the eclipse drops out, viz. those that are negative or surpass twice the middle value (44.5 for m' ; 34,48,0 for ψ), are more frequent in our computed than in the Chaldaean table. In other words, the Chaldaeans took the limits within which eclipses were possible, wider than corresponds to our computation. We may express this in a more exact numerical way. The average increase of E' between two eclipses, in 6 months, is $6 \times 2,2,40,58 - 12 = 0,16,5,48$. Between the limits $\pm 0,52,12$ fall, on the average, $1,44,24 : 0,16,5,48 = 6 \cdot 5$ eclipses. This is the average number of eclipses to be expected in the middle part of each group. For the real moon eclipses occur when the latitude is smaller than $57' 43''$, which for a mean inclination of $5^\circ 8' 7''$ corresponds to a distance $10^\circ 47'$ from the node. In 6 months the distance of full moon to node increases by $4^\circ \cdot 028^1$, hence we may expect between $-10^\circ 47'$ and $+10^\circ 47'$ an average number of $21 \cdot 57 : 4 \cdot 028 = 5 \cdot 4$ eclipses. Hence the Chaldaean astronomers have taken the limits for possible eclipses so much too wide that there is room in each group for $6 \cdot 5$ instead of for $5 \cdot 4$ eclipses. We might express it in this way, that for the sum total of the radius of moon and earth shadow a value is taken $\frac{5}{4}$ times too large, i. e. $1^\circ 9' \cdot 5$ instead of $57' \cdot 7$, nearly identical to our value computed above $1^\circ 12' \cdot 5$. We must, however, bear in mind that these results only express the ratio of the said sum total of diameters to the inclination of the orbit. If we consider that owing to the eccentricities of the orbits the apparent diameters vary and their sum total may reach $63' \cdot 6$, then we see that the Chaldaeans had to take their limits wider than corresponds to average conditions, in order to miss no eclipse, however small the obscured segment might be. Because the tables served for forecasting it can be understood that the beginning of the series of possible eclipses should be indicated by the salient value of zero for ψ , whereas at the end of a series such an indication was not necessary, because always 6 months after an eclipse the next one was looked for.

¹⁾ The Origin of the Saros, p. 947.

4. In Part III of his *Researches on Ancient Astronomy* Neugebauer devotes a special chapter to the saros¹). Against the common opinion that the Chaldaeans used a period under this name for the forecasting of eclipses he shows that this name for an eclipse period was not used in Babylon, nor by Greek authors either; that it is a modern invention, which has been copied quite uncritically by each author from another. In this point his criticism is convincing and definite. Moreover he treats the question of the saros itself and he denies that this period ever played a role in Chaldaean astronomy to forecast future eclipses. His arguments may be summarized in the following.

In cuneiform texts no mention is made of the saros method of prediction "Quite as little (i. e. nothing) is known of a use of the saros method from cuneiform sources. What we know from these sources are only systematic computations of the moon's motion in the mathematical astronomical texts; how before this stage of knowledge eclipses were predicted, we do not know" (p. 224). The present author considered the text No. 200 as an instance of this use. But it is easily seen that this table could be constructed from tables of the full moon just as has been the case with text No. 107, by copying from them all the full moons with smallest E'' values. The time of construction of 200, in the first century of the Seleucid Era is only a little earlier than the eclipse table 107 of system II, that covers the years 137—160 S. E. "This small distance of time already makes it very improbable that this text (200) should represent a more primitive former stage before the mathematical-astronomical texts" (p. 249).

If the function E'' of table 107 is computed for every month backward as far as the years of 200 (beginning 392 B. C.) we find that by excerpting the eclipses, a table nearly identical with 200 is obtained. The difference that at the most sensitive transition place, at Rs line 1, the 5 months interval is displaced over one line, has no real significance for the eclipses themselves. We even find that the beginning of 107 is removed a full number of periods of 223 months from the upper lines of 200. "Hence the grouping of eclipses, given by P. is seen to be an automatic consequence of the computing rule of E'' , so that it is not necessary to consider the list of text 200 as a protocol of observed and non-observed eclipses, and it is no "saros-canon" but simply represents the computed column Λ (year and month) of an eclipse text of the same type as 107. Thus the only text that could be looked at as a witness of the first stage of the saros-method, has been entirely inserted into the context of the well known theory of system II" (p. 253).

A much simpler preceding history of eclipse-computing can be outlined "for which it is not necessary to assume a systematic collecting and grouping of observations to periodic series of analogous phenomena. . . Doubtless it has been observed from the oldest times that eclipses only occur at full moon or new moon; also the fact that then the deviation of the moon from the ecliptic is very small, whereas with large latitudes of the moon eclipses do not occur, must be

¹) l. c. p. 241, 253.

remarked as soon as a beginning was made with systematically following the moon's course, what was forced very early already by the calendar. The essential step, procuring everything for a prediction of the eclipses, consists in the idea of connecting the two phenomena, syzygies and vicinity to the node, by means of a common cycle, just as syzygies and solar year are connected in the calendar cycles. . . ." (p. 245). The saros-relation $223 : 242$ can be found by simply counting during some 18 or 36 years the number of variations of latitude and of synodic months, whereas the saros-method of predicting eclipses necessitates the collection of a much larger mass of observational data.

It is not necessary to suppose the use at once of such highly developed moon tables as those of system II; simpler tables could have been used, and the use of zig-zag functions for periodic phenomena is found in some tablets of about 700 B. C. already. Kugler found the first calendar cycle to start 528 B. C., the 19-years-cycle 382 B. C. "From the middle of the 6th century on, all conditions are given for this historical development of eclipse prediction, and somewhere in the 5th century we may put the development of the mathematical-astronomical tables" (p. 246).

"The situation hence, in Babylonian astronomy, is the same as with Ptolemy, who also first develops the *theory* of the moon's motion and then as its consequence determines the possible distances between succeeding eclipses" (p. 248).

To these considerations and arguments it may be allowed to oppose the following remarks.

It is true that in the text **200**, in its preserved part, it is said with no word that it should serve for the prediction of eclipses by means of the saros period. The same is the case with nearly all the tables from this or later times, lunar as well as planetary. What was their purpose and use must be deduced entirely from the structure of their rows of figures themselves.

What is the structure of Table **200**? The successive groups of eclipses are arranged in parallel columns, each containing 38 eclipse moons in five groups with the same sequel of intervals. This arrangement shows clearly the knowledge of the larger period of 223 moons in the succession of the groups, and it emphasizes the importance of this period by repeating it five times and perhaps oftener. What can be the purpose of such an arrangement other than showing that by continuing the table we are able to indicate the future eclipses? Since the text must have been made after the death of the first Seleukos (it shows the new counting of years according to S. E. instead of to reigning kings) all the former columns represent observed or invisible eclipses of the past, back to 374 B. C., or assuming some columns to be broken off, to 410 B. C. How many of the later columns (certainly reaching till S. E. 46 (266 B. C.) but in the case of two columns to be broken off, till S. E. 82) represent predicted future phenomena we do not know.

Of course it is true that from an extensive table of full moons with their latitudes, of the kind of the later tables of system II, a table of eclipses such as **200** could be excerpted. But what reason would there be, in that case, first to

arrange them in columns of the saros period, and secondly to omit the data determining their character individually? In **200** this arrangement was necessary to indicate, by their position on the same lines, the return of the same size and character of the eclipse and the same succession. If a quantity indicating size and character and succession is copied from the complete fullmoontable, there is no need for this arrangement any more. Indeed No. **107**, derived in such a way and containing these individual data, shows no such an arrangement; its eclipses occupy $28+18=46$ lines, entirely omitting any saros indication. Instead of assuming such a table as **200** to be the coarsened and simplified excerpt of tables with a higher stage of knowledge and more details, it seems more probable that we have to consider it as the full representative of a more primitive stage of knowledge that went no farther than just what it offers. The oldest tables of system II known (No **114**)¹⁾ are from S. E. 124 (188 B. C.), not such an insignificant number of years later than the probable date of the "saros-canon"²⁾; the planetary tables of the same highly developed structure begin to appear first also at the same time, in the 2nd century B. C. Neugebauer makes the supposition that in the preceding centuries analogous tables of a more simple structure have existed, as precursors of the later more perfect ones. The possibility of such tables certainly must be admitted, but their existence is merely a hypothesis; no cuneiform texts conforming to it have been found so far. Moreover such tables would have contained at least one row of figures (latitude, or distance to the node) expressing the conditions of the phenomenon; and we can see no reason why in copying a table of eclipses from them this numerical value, expressing in the best way occurrence and character of the eclipse, should have been omitted. We do not pretend that the "saros-canon" expresses the full height of knowledge at the time of its construction, say 250 B. C.; often methods of former times are preserved and still used when better methods, perhaps of other schools, are already present. We say that it represents in itself an independent earlier stage of knowledge than the more extensive moon tables with more numerical details.

What we know about the early history of astronomy puts beyond any doubt that eclipses were observed and their phenomena were known long before there was any question of determining the moon's latitude. The very concept of latitude belongs to a far higher stage of scientific development. The ecliptic is not indicated as a visible line at the sky; exactly it is given only as the locus of the lunar eclipses, as is indicated by its name. Only gradually, in connection with

¹⁾ Neugebauer UAA part V, p. 411.

²⁾ Continuing the columns of **200** by simply computing the first date of each, by means of the rule that 235 moonperiods, 12 more than 223, form the calendar period of 19 years, we find (the years $19n+9$, $+7$, $+4$ having the 12th month repeated):

S. E. 28 XII, 46 XII, 64 XIIa, 83 I, 101 I, 119 I, 137 II,

the latter just the date of the first line of **107** — the connection between the two tables, discovered by Neugebauer by computing the full moons of system II back. So we could think of **107** as a later continuation, with more modern and better dates, of the old, more primitive table.

observations of the planets, a kind of middle line between the courses of the chief planets could present itself as a line of reference for northern or southern deviations. Moreover the observations of the moon in the first time restricted themselves to the disappearance and reappearance of the sickle moon and to the vicinity of the full moon, which was necessary for the calendar and the rites. We cannot assume the Babylonians to have proceeded from the ideas and methods of a highly developed science, so as to combine a knowledge of the nodes and a knowledge of the syzygies into a cycle of eclipses. On the contrary the eclipses were observed and well known long before any idea of latitudes or nodes or even cycles could arise; and their return after 6 months was the earliest experience, used in the Assyrian time already as a rule for predictions. The Babylonians did not look out for periods and assemble observations for that purpose. The observations were made for astrological purposes, as official duty: "When the king asks, what signs have you seen: . . ." The periods gradually imposed themselves spontaneously upon them, as their store of observational records increased. In this way in the long run of the centuries they must have perceived the groups of the consecutive eclipses, then the succession of always new groups, some with more, some with fewer eclipses, and still later the return of the same character after every 5 groups—and this without any measurement, any notion of latitude or node, any theory of the moon's motion being necessary. In a text book as Ptolemy's the logical order is to give first the theory and then to derive the phenomena from it. Always the most abstract fundamentals, which science has produced as its latest results, are put in the forefront of its theoretical explanation. But this is just the reverse of the historical order of development.

It seems to me that at the basis of our differences about the meaning of text 200 and the development of Chaldaean astronomy lies a different view on the mentality of these early astronomers. Neugebauer's argumentation is logical, if we consider them chiefly as primitive scientists, with minds and a mode of thinking analogous to ours, qualitatively the same, but quantitatively only in its beginnings, so that we see here the first origin and gradual growth of that which to us is familiar as scientific spirit and methods. If a modern scientist had to find means of forecasting the return of lunar eclipses, he certainly would find it to be more effective to observe during some dozens of years the latitude of the moon, its return to the node and the extreme latitudes, to compare it with the returns of the full moons, and to try to find a common multiple of these periods¹⁾, than to start a series of eclipse observations extending over several centuries. That point of view means that what we call the scientific mind, the looking to natural phenomena as an object for study, in order to find regularities and causal laws in it, is a new human property, arising spontaneously from imperceptible beginnings. In reality it is the outcome of the ordinary mental activities of primitive man, transformed and specialised, in the higher state of first civilisation, by the necessary social activities themselves. The history of

¹⁾ It must be born in mind, however, that to find the ratio 242 : 223 to be more exact than say 254 : 234 would need a longer period or greater accuracy than was available at that time.

Chaldaean astronomy owes its prominent place in the science of human development to the fact that here we have one of the rare cases, where step by step we can follow the primitive minds, that do not know of scientific aims, in the gradual development of the beginnings of science and scientific methods.

Primitive peoples all over the earth have and had a certain knowledge of celestial phenomena, because they need it for their life necessities. Travelling nomades and seafarers use the stars as guides on their wanderings. The moon period is used nearly everywhere for counting the time. The heliacal rising and setting of certain stars indicate the seasons with their different agricultural or hunting activities. Then in the regions of first civilisation, such as Mesopotamia, where powerful central governments arise, all these activities are centralised and intensified in the hands of a class of priests, the spiritual leaders of the social and economic organisation. Among other duties they had to watch in the sky the appearance and disappearance of the moon and the stars, in order to keep the calendar, the times of the rites and religious festivals in regular order. In that pure, nearly always splendidly clear sky, visible on all sides down to the horizon, where the stars moved in their regular course, their attention was captured by the brilliant planets, irregularly wandering to and fro as living beings through the starry landscape, dominated by that most brilliant luminary, the moon, in its ever changing aspects and positions. The celestial phenomena imposed themselves upon their mind as the most important, supreme world, where the chief gods, embodied in these luminaries, proclaimed and designated their rule over the earth and men. So astrology arose as a mighty world-conception. Belief in magic and signs is found in nearly all primitive peoples; belief in signs from the stars we find in Mesopotamia in the oldest time already¹). After 1000 B. C. it developed into a most important part of religious and social practice in the Assyrian time. It may be that the vicissitudes of the world politics of this power in its last centuries produced a special need for such divination. Regularly the priests in Babylon and the other cities are observing the celestial phenomena, i. e. are reading the messages of the gods, and send their reports to the court; most important are the irregular, unexpected happenings, the wanderings, stand-stills and encounters of the planets, the eclipses of sun and moon. Also the practical aims are included into this general conception; when the calendar deviates and full moon comes at the 12th instead of the 13th it is a bad omen. In these astronomical observations there is no trace of what we call a scientific view or aim; at that time as in the whole of antiquity the phenomena of nature are not treated with the concept of causality, but of finality. They are not considered as cause and result, but as sign, omen and meaning.

Hence no regularity or law is sought for. But regularities impose themselves without giving surprise. The regular returns of the lunar aspects were known of old. Now, during the high tide of astrological observations, new regularities, in the planets, in the eclipses, gradually fix themselves in the consciousness.

¹) Cf. the inscription of Gudea of Lagash, how the goddess Nisaba appears to him in a dream "the favorable star for the building of the temple she indicated".

They are included in the astrological practice as a contrivance, manifesting the increasing skill in predicting; in one of the reports it is said that the predicted eclipse was not visible, because it had taken place in the daytime already¹⁾. So in the 7th and 6th centuries these priests possess a certain knowledge of the periodicity and the periods of a number of phenomena. At this time we find also an increase of exactness of the observations: numerical values of the distances of the planets to one another and to the stars²⁾. In the then following centuries of Persian domination (say 550 to 300 B. C.) the astrological fervor seems to have declined; only now and then omens for the king appear between the astronomical data; but the habit of observing regularly the planets and the moon, as a part of ritual duties, is preserved and it even improved. Now the periods come to the front, embodying the astronomical knowledge. They are used to compile tables of future phenomena out of the past; "observations (or computations) for the festivals" they are called; and this simple method of constructing almanac data remains in use during all the later centuries. The calendar periods are introduced instead of empirically intercalating months by the risings and settings of the stars; the 8 years cycle, after Kugler, is used from 529 B. C. on, afterwards perhaps a 27 years cycle, and then from 373 B. C. onward the 19 years cycle. Now also the saros cycle emerges from the more simple groupings of eclipses.

An increasing exactness in describing the phenomena, by means of conjunctions with stars and distances, in the Persian and first Seleucidian centuries, then must have led to the most perfect stage, the construction of elaborate tables of the moon and the planets by ingenious and complicated mathematical methods, such as we know from the later Seleucidian and the Arsacidean time, after 200 B. C. This perfection, it is true, is of a purely formal-mathematical character; the old consecration formula: an omen of the gods Bel and Beltis, always being the introduction. And to produce the full height of ancient astronomy in Greece the knowledge, therein contained, had to be combined with the Greek philosophical and cosmological developments. And yet this perfection is so great, that we feel a certain abruptness in the appearance of these tables; we do not know on what observations of a more special and refined character they are based, and we might expect analogous but less perfect tables as precursors in the preceding century. We must hope that this gap will be filled by new texts. And our very schematical outline, though it seems to be in accordance with the data known at present, will certainly have to be corrected and specialised according as further texts are discovered and unravelled.

¹⁾ R. C. Thompson, The reports of the magicians and astrologers No. 275 A.

²⁾ VAT 4956 for 568 B. C., Strassm. 400 for 523 B. C.